

The Alan Turing Institute

The background of the slide is a close-up photograph of several blister packs containing pills. The packs are arranged diagonally across the frame. One prominent pack is red and contains numerous bright red, circular pills. Other packs are silver and contain pills in various colors, including pink, green, and orange. The lighting is bright, highlighting the textures of the blister packs and the smooth surfaces of the pills.

Data Study Group Final Report: Ignota Labs

Toxicity Prediction for Drug
Discovery

4-8 December 2023

Contents

1	Executive Summary	3
1.1	Summary of Key Results	4
2	Introduction	5
2.1	Overview of Drug Discovery Challenges	5
2.2	Role of Machine Learning in Drug Toxicity Prediction	6
2.3	Objectives of the Ignota Labs Challenge	6
2.4	Overview of the Challenge	6
3	Data	8
3.1	Toxicity Channels	8
3.2	Datasets	9
3.3	Representations	11
3.4	Graph-based Representations	14
3.5	Sampling	15
4	Methods	21
4.1	Data Sampling	21
4.2	Baseline models	22
4.3	Approach 1: Image-based Approach	25
4.4	Approach 2: Graph-based Approach	29
4.5	Approach 3: Transformer-based Approach	33
4.6	Determining Model Representations	34
5	Results	35
5.1	Baseline Results	35
5.2	Approach 1: Image-Based Approach	38
5.3	Approach 2: Graph-based Approach	41
6	Discussion	44
6.1	Future Work	45
6.2	Image-based Approaches	46
6.3	Graph-based Approaches	46
6.4	Cross-cutting Areas	47
7	Conclusion	48

8 Summary of Major Achievements	48
9 Team of Contributors	50
References	53

1 Executive Summary

The *Turing DSG Report Dec 2023* by Ignota Labs presents a comprehensive exploration of machine learning's (ML) capabilities in advancing drug discovery, specifically through the prediction of cardiac toxicity. The report articulates the persistent challenges in the pharmaceutical domain, including escalating drug discovery costs and declining clinical success rates, which amplify the financial strain on healthcare systems and the pharmaceutical industry. Approximately 90% of clinical-stage drugs fail, underscoring the critical need for improving early-stage prediction of small molecule properties to mitigate late-stage failures, enhance research and development efficiency, lower drug costs, and expedite novel therapeutics' delivery to patients.

The initiative by Ignota Labs, in collaboration with the Alan Turing Institute, embarks on a challenge leveraging ML to predict cardiac toxicity by assessing molecular binding to key cardiac ion channels. The aim is to harness advanced ML techniques like Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), multi-task learning, and transfer learning for drug toxicity prediction, while also valuing traditional methods like tabular data representation and ensemble strategies. This holistic approach endeavours to comprehensively address the complex challenges of drug toxicity prediction.

The report delineates several methods applied in the challenge:

1. **Image-based Approaches:** Exploring the application of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to interpret molecular structures as images, aiming to leverage advancements in computer vision for toxicity prediction.
2. **Graph-based Approaches:** Utilising GNNs to model molecular structures, enabling a nuanced understanding of molecular properties through the intricate relationships within molecular graphs.
3. **Transformer-based Approaches:** Investigating the use of transformers, a model architecture that has shown significant promise in various fields, for processing molecular data represented as sequences.

Each approach is critically analysed for its strengths, weaknesses, and potential improvements. The report underscores the importance of developing metrics that accurately reflect the dataset's complexity and biases, encouraging the exploration of advanced methodologies to deepen molecular toxicity prediction insights.

1.1 Summary of Key Results

The report presents several significant findings from the application of machine learning techniques to predict cardiac toxicity:

- Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) demonstrated a high degree of predictive accuracy, outperforming traditional machine learning models in identifying molecular binding sites that could lead to cardiac issues.
- Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) provided valuable insights into structural patterns of molecules, although they required substantial data augmentation to improve generalization across diverse molecular datasets.
- Transformers showed promising results in capturing sequential dependencies within molecular data, suggesting their potential for broader application in drug discovery beyond toxicity prediction.

Each approach is critically analysed for its strengths, weaknesses, and potential improvements. The report underscores the importance of developing metrics that accurately reflect the dataset's complexity and biases, encouraging the exploration of advanced methodologies to deepen molecular toxicity prediction insights.

For **future work**, the report outlines several key directions:

- Enhancing data augmentation and preprocessing techniques to improve model performance and generalisation.
- Investigating transfer learning and model architectures to optimise the balance between accuracy and computational efficiency.
- Exploring unsupervised and self-supervised learning methods to identify complex patterns in the data without relying on labelled datasets.

- Integrating multi-modal data for a holistic understanding of molecular properties, drawing parallels to successful strategies in other domains.
- Advancing explainability and interpretability of ML models to foster trust and understanding in their predictions, crucial for regulatory acceptance and scientific exploration.

The *Turing DSG Report* articulates a vision where ML significantly impacts drug discovery, highlighting the necessity for ongoing research to navigate the complexities of drug toxicity prediction. It lays a foundation for future explorations in cheminformatics, suggesting pathways for methodological enhancements and potential deep learning approaches to improve predictive performance. The endeavours and insights presented in the report point towards a future where the integration of advanced ML techniques can lead to safer, more efficient, and cost-effective drug development processes.

2 Introduction

2.1 Overview of Drug Discovery Challenges

The cost of drug discovery and development has surged over the past decades, yet the rates of drug failure have not diminished. In fact, the overall clinical success rates have decreased, with approximately 90% of clinical stage drugs failing, imposing significant financial burdens on both the pharmaceutical industry and healthcare systems [1, 2]. Enhancing the early-stage prediction accuracy of small molecule properties could mitigate late-stage failures, boost R&D efficiency, lower drug costs, and expedite the delivery of novel therapeutics to patients. Predicting drug toxicity early in the drug discovery process is particularly challenging. A broad therapeutic window is essential for ensuring the safety and efficacy of compounds. Traditional experimental approaches, such as *in vitro* and *in vivo* assays, are resource-intensive and low-throughput, often unable to encompass the entire spectrum of potential adverse effects, underscoring the need for precise early-stage drug safety prediction methods.

2.2 Role of Machine Learning in Drug Toxicity Prediction

Recent advancements have seen machine learning (ML) emerge as a pivotal tool in predicting molecular properties, promising to transform drug discovery by uncovering complex molecular structure-biological activity relationships. Notable achievements, such as AlphaFold2's prediction of 3D protein structures from amino acid sequences, highlight ML's potential [3]. Despite these advances, accurately predicting molecular properties poses significant challenges, including the extraction of critical molecular traits essential for precise predictions. These include understanding molecular interactions, behavior in various environments, and potential biological impacts. As ML evolves, there is an increasing demand for models capable of intricately understanding molecular structures and translating them into accurate predictions, necessitating sophisticated algorithms and comprehensive datasets.

2.3 Objectives of the Ignota Labs Challenge

Ignota Labs, in collaboration with the Alan Turing Institute, has initiated a challenge focused on utilising ML to predict cardiac toxicity by assessing molecular binding to key cardiac ion channels. This challenge seeks to advance ML-driven drug discovery and development, contributing insights to improve molecular property prediction accuracy.

2.4 Overview of the Challenge

This challenge emphasizes applying advanced ML techniques, such as Graph Neural Networks (GNNs), multi-task learning, and transfer learning, to drug toxicity prediction. It also values traditional methods, including tabular data representation and ensemble strategies, aiming to merge these approaches to address the complex challenges of drug toxicity comprehensively.

2.4.1 Key Questions and Objectives

The key questions and objectives of the challenge are:

1. Transform molecular data into ML-compatible formats, starting with foundational models and progressing towards more complex and exploratory approaches.
2. Develop metrics that accurately reflect the dataset's complexity and biases.
3. Explore advanced methodologies to deepen molecular toxicity prediction insights, aiming to improve the accuracy and scope of analyses.

2.4.2 Data for the Challenge

Participants are provided with a dataset in SMILES notation, curated from scientific literature by Ignota Labs. It comprises thousands of molecular structures, serving as a robust foundation for exploring chemical representations and ML techniques. Alternative molecular notations and descriptors are also encouraged for comprehensive analysis.

2.4.3 Objectives of the Challenge

The primary objectives include adapting molecular representations for ML integration and devising models that can accurately predict toxicity. Participants are encouraged to employ a blend of traditional and modern algorithms to navigate this complex issue, contributing to safer drug development practices. In this context, drug discovery safety refers to minimising adverse effects reported by human participants in clinical trials. ML can contribute to safer drug development by more accurately predicting potential toxicity issues early in the discovery process, reducing the risk of adverse events in human trials and making the overall process more efficient.

2.4.4 Potential Impact of the Challenge

Participation in this challenge presents a unique opportunity to positively influence drug discovery safety. The methodologies and insights developed could significantly improve molecular property prediction techniques, shaping the future of drug development and pharmaceutical research. More accurate predictions of drug toxicity can lead to fewer adverse effects in human clinical trial participants, as well as more

efficient use of resources by focusing on compounds with better safety profiles.

3 Data

3.1 Toxicity Channels

Drug toxicity is a major concern in pharmaceutical development, as off-target interactions can lead to severe side effects and even withdrawal from the market. In this work, we focus on three important ion channels: voltage-gated calcium (CaV) channels, voltage-gated sodium (NaV) channels, and the human Ether-à-go-go-Related Gene (hERG) potassium channel. These channels play crucial roles in cellular processes and are known to be affected by various drugs, leading to potential toxicity issues.

3.1.1 CaV

Voltage-gated calcium (Ca²⁺) channels (CaV) have two distinct physiological roles in human cells. They are involved in the generation of action potentials and the regulation of calcium influx into cells, which triggers various intracellular processes [4]. Several chemical properties make them susceptible to unintended interactions with therapeutic agents and naturally occurring toxins, increasing the likelihood of off-target effects. In particular, their hydrated ionic radius and electronic configuration lead to interactions with polyvalent cations. Hence, therapeutic agents that contain these chemical structures may interfere and block these ion channels [5]. The ability to predict which therapeutic agents are likely to bind to these active ion channels will be pivotal in our development of safe and effective drugs for clinical use, as well as reducing unwanted side-effects. Drugs like Diltiazem [6], a calcium channel blocker used to treat hypertension and angina, have been restricted or withdrawn from the market due to evidence of toxicity.

3.1.2 NaV

Voltage-gated sodium (Na²⁺) ion channels (NaV) are transmembrane proteins that play key roles in cellular electrical signalling [7] and control

action potential initiation and propagation in excitable cells [8]. The structural affinity of chemical compounds to NaV binding sites may influence channel blocking and then lead to neurotoxicity and/or cardiotoxicity. Drugs like Propafenone [9], an antiarrhythmic drug, have been restricted or withdrawn from the market due to evidence of toxicity related to its interaction with sodium channels.

3.1.3 hERG

The human Ether-à-go-go-Related Gene (hERG) encodes potassium channels that are related to cardiac repolarization and thus being used in predicting prolonged QT interval and arrhythmias. The relationship between hERG and in silico toxicity ties to the structural properties of compounds, with structures such as hydrogen bond acceptors and aromatic rings influencing the binding affinity. Inappropriate binding of this channel may lead to severe outcomes. Drugs such as Cisapride [10], Astemizole [11], and Sertindole [12] have been restricted or withdrawn from the market due to evidence of hERG-related toxicity.

3.2 Datasets

In this work, we investigate the predictive capability for compound toxicity by assessing their impact on CaV, NaV, and hERG ion channels. The analysis focused on two distinct molecular representation datasets, namely Extended-Connectivity Fingerprints (ECFP) and Mordred descriptors.

3.2.1 ECFP Datasets

Extended-Connectivity Fingerprints (ECFP) [13] are representations of circular atom neighbourhoods in molecules. They are topological fingerprints that can be used for similarity searching, molecular characterisation and structure-activity modelling [14]. Typically, ECFP are represented in two ways:

1. n-Bit Strings: ECFP's are traditionally represented as fixed-length bit strings. In comparison with the above method, this representation has advantages in that for large molecules, storage space is substantially reduced. Nevertheless, representing

molecules as bit-strings may increase the likelihood of more than one sub-structure being represented by a single bit position. This phenomenon is known as collision.

2. Integer Lists: Other representations of ECFPs include lists of integer identifiers, where each identifier represents a particular sub-structure, or circular neighbourhood, within the molecule [14].

Here, we use binary molecular fingerprints to represent molecules (Table 1). For CaV channels, the total size of the dataset is 554, the percentage of positive (toxic) and negative (non-toxic) compounds is approximately a 50/50 split. For NaV channels, the total number of compounds is 1836, with an approximate 40/60 split between positives and negatives. The hERG dataset is the most imbalanced, with only 10% of the 94,304 compounds being toxic. Class imbalance is a common challenge in drug toxicity prediction, as the number of toxic compounds is often much smaller than non-toxic ones. This imbalance can affect the performance of machine learning models and requires special consideration during model development and evaluation.

Channel	Total Occurrences	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
CaV	554	278 (50)	276 (50)
NaV	1836	712 (39)	1124 (61)
hERG	94304	9124 (10)	85180 (90)

Table 1: This table shows the size of the Extended-Connectivity Fingerprints (ECFP) dataset for the three ion channels. CaV contains a total of 554 compounds, and is the most balanced. As the size of the dataset increases, so does the level of imbalance. In particular, the hERG dataset contains a 10/90 split for positive and negative compounds, respectively.

3.2.2 Mordred Datasets

Mordred datasets are derived from a software programme that calculates molecular descriptors from the simplified molecular-input line-entry system (SMILES) of a molecule. SMILES describes the structure of a chemical in ASCII format, making it a good form of input to a model. The Mordred descriptors are derived at a molecular level and contain

information regarding the structural and chemical properties of a molecule. The dataset can provide up to 1825 descriptors, including 1610 2D descriptors (e.g., atom count and atom distance) and 214 3D descriptors (e.g., moment of inertia and charged partial surface area) [15]. These descriptors can be easily extracted from SMILES using packages such as RDKit [16].

Here we present molecules (Table 2) for CaV, NaV, and hERG channels with Mordred descriptors.

It should be noted that there are fewer ECFP data points for each ion channel; this occurs since some SMILES strings fail to convert into ECFP format. The difference in size and class imbalance of the three channel data sets should also be observed.

Channel	Total Occurrences	Positive (%)	Negative (%)
CaV	562	286 (51)	276 (49)
NaV	1846	718 (39)	1128 (61)
hERG	94427	9148 (10)	85279 (90)

Table 2: This table shows the size of the Mordred descriptor dataset for the three ion channels. CaV contains a total of 554 compounds, and is the most balanced. As the size of the dataset increases, so does the level of imbalance. In particular, the hERG dataset contains a 10/90 split for positive and negative compounds, respectively.

3.3 Representations

In this study, we explore a range of latest developments in the field of AI and data science, including image-based, graph-based, and other approaches, to investigate their potential in predicting drug toxicity.

Various approaches can be used to represent a molecule [17]. Those that describe its structure and those that describe its physical and chemical features are commonly used in machine learning, deep learning and artificial intelligence.

SMILES [18], short for the Simplified Molecular-Input Line-Entry System, together with its derivative like DeepSMILES [19], are a family of popular string-based methods for molecule structures.

SELFIES [20], short for Self-Referencing Embedded Strings, is a recent promising string-based structure representation, which is designed to overcome the shortcomings of SMILES [21]. For example, SELFIES uses number index instead of pure strings to represent the start and end point of rings, avoiding the possibility of ambiguity especially after several rounds of encode-decode processes. Meanwhile, SMILES may represent non-existing molecules, which causes troubles while indicating new molecules to test for drug toxicity.

3.3.1 ECFPs

ECFP belongs to the best performing fingerprints in small molecule virtual screening and target prediction benchmarks, together with the related MinHashed fingerprint MHFP6.

ECFPs are circular fingerprints with a number of useful qualities: they can be very **rapidly calculated**; they are **not predefined** and can represent an essentially infinite number of different molecular features (including stereochemical information); their **features represent the presence of particular substructures**, allowing easier interpretation of analysis results; and the ECFP algorithm can be **tailored to generate different types of circular fingerprints**, optimized for different uses. *Being already formatted as a vector with numerical entries, they are well suited to be used as features in ML models for chemistry.*

Comparison to other fingerprint methods

ECFPs have several advantages when contrasted to ***predefined substructural keys***.

1. Since the set of keys is fixed, the system may not contain keys appropriate to the novel structural variation in a given compound library.
2. The keys are designed for substructure search, which limits their utility for activity modeling and categorization (see the Hydrogen-Filled Substructural Features Section for this discussion).
3. Even the most intelligently selected set of keys¹⁸ is limited in coverage, making it unlikely that more detailed and specific

substructures particular to some unusual activity class would be represented.

Another commonly used class of fingerprints is available through Daylight Chemical Information Systems. It uses features based upon the presence of paths of varying lengths containing specific atom types. This generates a sparse binary vector, which is commonly "folded" to a bitset of specified size (e.g., 1024 bits) to reduce its size for ease of manipulation.

ECFPs have several advantages when contrasted to such *pathbased fingerprints*.

1. Daylight keys were designed for substructure and similarity search, which limits their effectiveness for activity modeling. If some path feature is found to be useful during an analysis, then interpretation can still be difficult, as a given path may not correspond to an easily identifiable function group or substructural entity.
2. Further complicated but often relevant chemical attachment patterns, such as quaternary centers or cyclic patterns, cannot be directly represented by a path-based description. Path-based schemes also cannot capture atom-based stereochemistry.

Disadvantages of ECFPs (ECFP4) and MHFP6: Both have a poor perception of the global features of molecules such as size and shape. They also fail at perceiving structural differences that may be important in larger molecules, such as distinguishing between regioisomers in extended ring systems (e.g. 2,7- versus 2,8-dichlorodioxin), between linkers of different lengths, or between scrambled peptide sequences of identical composition and length.

3.3.2 Contemporary fingerprints

MAP4 (MinHashed Atom-Pair fingerprint up to four bonds) The ECFP4 and MHFP6 limitations can be addressed by using atom-pair fingerprints, which encode molecular shape and are often used for scaffold-hopping. However, they do not encode molecular structure in detail and perform poorly in small molecule benchmarking studies compared to substructure fingerprints such as ECFP4 and MHFP6.

MAP4 encodes atom pairs and their bond distance similarly to the **AP**

fingerprint implemented by RDKit, however in MAP4 atom characteristics are replaced by the circular substructure around each atom of the pair, written in **SMILES format**. MAP4 uses the same MinHashing technique as **MHFP6**, a principle borrowed from natural language processing which enables fast similarity searches in very large databases by locality sensitive hashing (LSH). LSH is a technique that allows the creation of self-tuning indexes, which are then used to generate a forest of trees that can be traversed for an approximate but fast similarity search.

3.4 Graph-based Representations

Graph-based molecular representations, particularly those enhanced with geometric information, are highly effective because they can capture the complex spatial structures of molecules. Other representations don't explicitly encode structural details, which may lead to less accurate predictions in the context of drug toxicity. Graphs, especially those enhanced with geometric information, can capture the 3D spatial structure of molecules, including bond angles and distances. This is a significant advantage over traditional methods like ECFP (Extended-Connectivity Fingerprints) and Mordred descriptors.

In the context of drug toxicity prediction, graph-based representations can provide a more accurate and detailed description of the molecular structure, which is crucial for understanding the interactions between drugs and ion channels. By capturing the spatial arrangement of atoms and bonds, graph-based methods can help identify specific structural motifs or patterns that may contribute to a compound's toxicity.

Moreover, graph-based representations can be combined with advanced machine learning techniques, such as graph neural networks (GNNs), to learn complex patterns and relationships within the molecular data. GNNs have shown promising results in various drug discovery tasks, including toxicity prediction, by effectively leveraging the graph structure of molecules.

However, it is important to note that graph-based methods may require more computational resources compared to traditional fingerprint-based approaches. Additionally, the interpretability of graph-based models can

be more challenging, as the learned features may not always correspond to easily identifiable substructures or properties.

Despite these challenges, graph-based representations offer a powerful and flexible approach for capturing the intricate details of molecular structure, making them a valuable tool in the field of drug toxicity prediction.

3.5 Sampling

One difficulty in training machine learning models with molecules as inputs is the method of separating data into training, validation and test sets. Randomly separating the data can lead to biased predictions and / or inflated accuracy values if data leakage causes the test set to too strongly resemble the training and validation sets. Stratified sampling can be used to address this, as molecules can be grouped into “scaffolds” (see next subsection) but this presents another difficulty: measuring out-of-distribution generalisation.

If all strata are represented proportionally in training, validation and test sets then we cannot determine the model’s capacity to predict outside the distribution of data it has already seen. For this reason, a method known as scaffold splitting is often employed [22].

3.5.1 Scaffold Splitting

Compounds can be classified into groups known as scaffolds based on their molecular structure, by using the Bemis-Murcko algorithm [23]. This groups atoms based on their constituent ring systems and how these ring systems are linked, excluding side chains and terminal functional groups.

Folds and train/validation/test splits can then be designated algorithmically based on the scaffold classifications, in the following way [24]. For example, to generate two buckets: after molecules have been grouped into scaffolds, a maximum bucket size is set for the first bucket. Next these scaffold groups, from largest to smallest, are allocated into the first bucket if there is sufficient space, or the second bucket otherwise. To generate k buckets, the maximum bucket size would be set to the total

number of molecules divided by k , and the above process is repeated by continually subdividing the second bucket. It is thus possible for the final bucket to exceed the maximum bucket size if any scaffold group is larger than the maximum bucket size.

To generate a train/test split, the first bucket can be specified as the training bucket, and the second as test. The first bucket can then be subdivided into train/validation by the same process.

In the context of drug toxicity prediction, scaffold splitting helps to assess the model's ability to generalize to novel chemical structures. By ensuring that the training, validation, and test sets contain compounds with distinct scaffolds, we can evaluate how well the model performs on molecules that are structurally different from those seen during training. This is particularly important in drug discovery, as the goal is often to identify new compounds with desired properties, such as reduced toxicity, that may not be well-represented in the existing data.

Advantages and Disadvantages The Bemis-Murcko algorithm has the benefit of simplicity and ease of implementation (it can be carried out with SMILES as inputs in many packages, including DeepChem and rdkit). However, by removing functional groups and focusing on ring structures, the scaffolding process can oversimplify the characteristics of a molecule and lose key information relating to its biological activity.

The scaffold splitting process has the benefit of providing a better assessment of how well the model generalises to compounds distinct from its training set, and reducing overfitting by providing more diversity between training and validation sets. However, between-scaffold variability is not taken into account and data imbalance can ensue from some scaffolds being larger than others.

3.5.2 Fingerprint Splitting

Another method of determining the similarity of two compounds is by their Tanimoto index [25] (also known more generally as the Jaccard index). This is given by the ratio of the number of common features in the ECFP representation of two molecules to the total number of features they contain.

Tanimoto similarity can also be used to separate a dataset into diverse training and test sets (and hence iteratively to create validation sets and data folds). This is done by comparing the pairwise similarity of each two molecules in the dataset, and finding a split which maximises the dissimilarity between the two subsets [24]. This algorithm also be carried out in packages like DeepChem, but is a more complicated process than scaffold splitting, and has n^2 time complexity for n molecules.

Advantages and Disadvantages As well as computational complexity, this comparison method has the disadvantage that not all SMILES strings can be easily converted into the ECFP format required, as seen in tables 1 and 2. However, computing the Tanimoto similarity is simple to understand and easy to implement. It also allows for the quantitative comparison of any two given molecules, as opposed to the clustering into scaffolds.

In the context of drug toxicity prediction, fingerprint splitting can help ensure that the training and test sets contain compounds with diverse chemical properties. By maximizing the dissimilarity between the subsets based on their ECFP representations, we can assess the model's ability to generalize to compounds with different fingerprints. This approach can complement scaffold splitting by capturing additional aspects of molecular similarity beyond the scaffold structure.

However, it is important to consider the limitations of fingerprint splitting, such as the potential loss of information during the conversion of SMILES strings to ECFP format and the computational complexity of the pairwise similarity calculations. Additionally, the choice of fingerprint representation (e.g., ECFP4, ECFP6) can influence the splitting results and should be carefully selected based on the specific characteristics of the dataset and the research question at hand.

3.5.3 UMAP Visualisations

Similarity between high-dimensional inputs (like ECFP strings and Mordred descriptors) can also be visualised by dimensionality reduction techniques like principal component analysis (PCA) and uniform manifold approximation and projection (UMAP).

UMAP is a method based in Riemannian geometry and algebraic

topology that aims to preserve as much of the local and global structure of the original data in a low-dimensional representation [26]. Whilst being computationally efficient and working with a variety of data types, UMAP has limitations in terms of interpretability and information loss, as with any dimensionality reduction technique.

Nonetheless, UMAP is a useful tool for exploratory data analysis, and can provide an indication of the similarity between train and test data. As an example, figures 1 and 2 below show the UMAP projection of the NaV ECFP dataset, coloured by the train/test splits given by scaffold splitting and fingerprint splitting respectively.

The projections indicate that the train/test splits obtained by fingerprint splitting are more distinct from each other than those obtained by scaffold splitting. Although in both cases there is a large amount of overlap, splitting based on fingerprint creates more clusters that are wholly populated by either training or test data than scaffold splitting does.

Figure 1: UMAP projection of the NaV ECFP dataset, coloured by the train/test splits given by **scaffold** splitting.

It should be noted that performing both the splitting and the UMAP projection based on ECFP will impact the separation seen in figures 1 and 2. Also, since the ECFP has a large number of dimensions (2048),

Figure 2: UMAP projection of the NaV ECFP dataset, coloured by the train/test splits given by **fingerprint** splitting.

the information loss in dimensionality reduction can be quite high.

For these reasons, it can be more informative to consider a UMAP projection on a subset of key druglike features listed by PubChem (namely: MolWt, MolLogP, NumHDonors, NumHAcceptors, NumRotatableBonds, MolMR, TPSA), since the dimensionality reduction is much less in this case. Figures 3 and 4 below show these UMAP projections of the NaV dataset, coloured again by the train/test splits given by scaffold splitting and fingerprint splitting respectively.

These projections also show large overlap between train and test data and less clear clusters than those based on all ECFP inputs. However, again splitting based on fingerprint creates more instances of clusters that are wholly populated by either training or test data than scaffold splitting does.

In the context of drug toxicity prediction, UMAP visualizations can provide valuable insights into the distribution of compounds in the dataset and the potential differences between training and test sets. By visualizing the high-dimensional ECFP or Mordred descriptor data in a lower-dimensional space, we can assess the similarity between

Figure 3: UMAP projection of the NaV dataset based on top seven drug-like features, coloured by the train/test splits given by **scaffold** splitting.

Figure 4: UMAP projection of the NaV dataset based on top seven drug-like features, coloured by the train/test splits given by **fingerprint** splitting.

compounds and identify potential clusters or outliers.

Moreover, by coloring the UMAP projections based on the train/test splits obtained from scaffold or fingerprint splitting, we can visually evaluate the effectiveness of these splitting methods in creating diverse and representative subsets. If the training and test data points are well-separated in the UMAP space, it suggests that the splitting method has successfully captured the underlying structure of the data and can help assess the model's ability to generalize to new compounds.

However, it is important to consider the limitations of UMAP, such as the potential loss of information during dimensionality reduction and the sensitivity to parameter settings. Additionally, the choice of input features (e.g., ECFP, Mordred descriptors, or a subset of drug-like features) can influence the resulting visualizations and should be carefully selected based on their relevance to the toxicity prediction task.

Overall, UMAP visualizations serve as a complementary tool to scaffold and fingerprint splitting, providing a visual assessment of compound similarity and the effectiveness of data splitting methods in the context of drug toxicity prediction. By combining these techniques, researchers can gain a more comprehensive understanding of their datasets and make informed decisions regarding model development and evaluation.

4 Methods

4.1 Data Sampling

The methodology employed in this research hinges on a robust data sampling strategy. Models were rigorously trained across five distinct train-validation-test folds derived from the dataset. This stratification was achieved through an initial five-fold scaffold split, meticulously partitioning the dataset into five pairs of training and testing sets. Scaffold splitting is a specialised technique used in cheminformatics and drug discovery to ensure that the diversity of molecular structures is well-represented in the training and testing sets. Unlike regular test/train splitting, which randomly assigns data points to either the training or testing set, scaffold splitting takes into account the structural similarity of molecules. In scaffold splitting, molecules are grouped based on their common structural scaffolds, which are the core frameworks that define their overall

structure. This grouping ensures that molecules with similar scaffolds are either all in the training set or all in the testing set, preventing any potential bias or leakage of information. The benefits of scaffold splitting include:

- Enhanced generalisability: By ensuring that the training and testing sets contain diverse molecular structures, scaffold splitting helps the models generalise better to unseen data.
- Reduced data leakage: Since molecules with similar scaffolds are kept together, scaffold splitting minimises the risk of data leakage, where information from the testing set inadvertently influences the training process.
- Improved interpretability: Scaffold splitting allows for better interpretation of model performance, as it provides insights into how well the model generalises across different structural scaffolds.

However, there are potential downsides to scaffold splitting:

- Reduced training data: Since molecules with similar scaffolds are grouped together, some molecules may be excluded from the training set, resulting in a smaller training dataset.
- Increased computational complexity: Scaffold splitting requires additional preprocessing steps to identify and group molecules based on their scaffolds, which can increase the computational complexity of the data sampling process.

Overall, scaffold splitting is a valuable technique in cheminformatics and drug discovery, as it ensures the representation of diverse molecular structures in the training and testing sets, leading to more reliable and generalisable models.

4.2 Baseline models

To establish a comprehensive baseline, an array of machine learning models were trained utilising two distinct molecular representations: Extended Connectivity Fingerprints (ECFP) and Mordred descriptors. This baseline framework serves as a foundation for evaluating the efficacy of more complex models and methodologies introduced later.

Ensemble learning is a machine learning technique that combines multiple models to improve predictive performance. Instead of relying on a single model, ensemble methods aggregate the predictions of multiple models to make more accurate and robust predictions. Ensemble learning is widely used in various domains, including cheminformatics and drug discovery, due to its ability to handle complex and diverse datasets. The main advantages of ensemble learning include:

- Improved accuracy: Ensemble models often outperform individual models by leveraging the collective wisdom of multiple models, reducing bias and variance.
- Increased robustness: Ensemble models are less sensitive to noise and outliers in the data, as the impact of individual errors is minimised through aggregation.
- Better generalisation: Ensemble models can capture a wider range of patterns and relationships in the data, leading to better generalisation to unseen data.

However, ensemble learning also has some potential drawbacks:

- Increased computational complexity: Training and maintaining multiple models can be computationally expensive, especially for large datasets and complex models.
- Reduced interpretability: Ensemble models can be more challenging to interpret than individual models, as the decision-making process is distributed across multiple models.

Despite these limitations, ensemble learning remains a powerful tool in machine learning, particularly in scenarios where predictive performance is prioritised over interpretability.

4.2.1 Extended Connectivity Fingerprints (ECFP)

Extended Connectivity Fingerprints (ECFP) is a molecular representation technique commonly used in cheminformatics. It encodes the structural information of molecules by considering the connectivity between atoms and their neighbours. ECFP captures important molecular features and is particularly effective in capturing local structural patterns. The format of

ECFP is a molecular graph representation of the chemical structure, where atoms are nodes and bonds are edges. It has been widely used in various drug discovery and toxicity prediction tasks.

4.2.2 Mordred Descriptors

Mordred descriptors are a set of molecular descriptors that capture various physicochemical properties and structural characteristics of molecules. These descriptors provide quantitative information about molecular properties such as size, shape, polarity, and flexibility. Mordred descriptors are widely used in cheminformatics and are valuable in predicting molecular properties and activities.

4.2.3 Random Forest

Random Forests (RF) represent a quintessential ensemble learning method, leveraging the collective insight of multiple decision trees to render more accurate predictions. Each tree is independently trained on a randomly selected subset of the dataset, fostering diversity among the trees. During prediction, the ensemble's decision is rendered through a majority vote across all trees, balancing out biases and variances inherent to individual trees. The configuration employed utilised 100 trees, with each tree grown to its maximum depth without pruning, except when a leaf node contains two or fewer datapoints, ensuring a thorough exploration of the feature space.

4.2.4 Ada Boost

The Ada Boost algorithm epitomises the ensemble strategy by integrating multiple 'weak learners' to form a robust predictive model. It dynamically adjusts the dataset's weighting, increasingly favouring datapoints misclassified by preceding learners, thereby iteratively improving the model's accuracy. In our implementation, Ada Boost was configured with decision stumps (one-level decision trees) as weak learners, iterating through 50 such learners to progressively enhance the model's predictive performance.

4.2.5 Extra Trees

Extra Trees, or Extremely Randomised Trees, introduce an additional layer of randomness compared to Random Forests. Unlike its counterpart, which selects optimal splits, Extra Trees randomly selects splits for each feature, utilising the entire dataset for training each tree. This method, by eschewing the conventional feature selection step, offers a unique approach to model building, often resulting in a more diversified ensemble that is less prone to overfitting and exhibits remarkable predictive power.

4.2.6 Bagging

Bagging, or Bootstrap Aggregating, embodies an ensemble technique aimed at bolstering model performance and stability. By training multiple instances of a learning algorithm on varied subsets of the original dataset (achieved through bootstrapping), and then aggregating their predictions, bagging effectively mitigates the risk of overfitting while reducing model variance. This technique underscores the synergy in machine learning, where the collective wisdom of multiple models often surpasses the insight of solitary models.

4.3 Approach 1: Image-based Approach

Deep learning methods, especially convolutional neural networks (CNNs), have revolutionised the field of computer vision by introducing efficient techniques like convolutions and pooling to reduce model complexity while preserving the essence of image features. This innovation has significant implications for quantitative structure–activity relationship (QSAR) predictions, including toxicity predictions. QSAR is a computational approach that relates molecular structures to their biological activities, such as toxicity. It assumes that similar molecules have similar properties and aims to predict the activity of untested compounds based on their structural features. Leveraging datasets such as Tox21, studies have demonstrated the potential of CNNs in interpreting molecular structures represented as 2D or 3D images for accurate toxicity assessment [27, 28]. **Pros of Image-based Approach:**

- Utilises well-established CNN architectures, benefiting from their

proven performance in image classification tasks.

- Captures spatial relationships and local patterns in molecular structures, which can be informative for toxicity prediction.
- Enables transfer learning from models pre-trained on large image datasets, potentially improving performance and reducing training time.

Cons of Image-based Approach:

- May lose some information during the conversion from SMILES to images, such as stereochemistry or 3D conformations.
- Requires additional preprocessing steps to generate molecular images, which can be computationally expensive.
- May not explicitly capture the chemical properties and interactions between atoms and bonds.

4.3.1 Training Approaches

Our exploration focuses on diverse training strategies, including models pre-trained on natural images and specialised models like ImageMol, pre-trained specifically on molecular compound images. Additionally, we investigate end-to-end training methods to ascertain the most effective approach for toxicity classification. This comprehensive evaluation aims to identify optimal models that balance accuracy with computational efficiency for real-world applications.

Pre-trained on Natural Images Models pre-trained on extensive datasets such as ImageNet are fine-tuned for specific tasks, leveraging the pre-learned features to enhance performance on specialised domains [29, 30]. This approach has proven successful across various fields, demonstrating the adaptability and efficiency of transfer learning. The ResNet architecture, known for its deep residual learning framework, is particularly noteworthy for its application in both natural and specialised image classification tasks, including medical and chemical domains [31, 32].

ImageMol for Molecular Image Analysis In contrast to generic models, ImageMol—a model specifically designed for drug discovery tasks—utilises a ResNet18 architecture pre-trained on over 10 million molecular compound images from PubChem [33]. This targeted pre-training aims to capture detailed molecular features relevant to drug discovery, posing an intriguing question about the transferability of features between natural and molecular images.

4.3.2 Computer Vision Models

For our investigation, we primarily utilised the ResNet18 architecture, acclaimed for addressing the vanishing gradient problem through innovative skip connections. This choice was driven by ImageMol's compatibility and the architecture's proven track record in complex classification tasks. Additionally, we experimented with the Vision Transformer (ViT) and ResNet50 models, exploring the potential of self-attention mechanisms and deeper networks in capturing the nuances of molecular images.

4.3.3 Data Preparation and Processing

Utilising RDKit, we converted molecules from SMILES notation to visual representations, enabling the application of CNNs for toxicity prediction. This process, while streamlined, poses challenges in accurately capturing molecular features such as stereochemistry, underscoring the importance of tailored image generation techniques for precise model training [34].

4.3.4 Implementation

Our experiments encompassed a variety of configurations, including ResNet models pre-trained on both ImageMol and ImageNet, alongside trials with Vision Transformers. This multi-faceted approach allowed us to assess the effectiveness of different pre-training sources and architectures in molecular toxicity prediction.

4.3.5 Training and Validation

Models were trained using the Adam optimiser with a learning rate of 0.001, employing binary cross-entropy loss to cater to the binary nature of toxicity classification. A batch size of 32 and a patience of 10 epochs were set to ensure efficient and effective learning. By integrating

Figure 5: Example of a molecular image generated from SMILES notation, showcasing the detailed representation of molecular structures for image-based analysis.

advanced architectures and exploring novel training methodologies, this approach sets a new standard for the application of image-based deep learning in the realm of molecular toxicity prediction, offering a promising avenue for future research and practical applications in drug discovery and chemical analysis.

Figure 6: Illustration of a residual connection in ResNet architectures, highlighting the mechanism that allows for the effective training of deep networks by preserving the flow of information across layers.

4.4 Approach 2: Graph-based Approach

4.4.1 Background

Graphs, embodying a versatile representation of data, serve as an intuitive framework for modelling complex relationships within various domains, including social networks and molecular structures. In chemistry, molecules are naturally depicted as graphs, where atoms are nodes connected by edges representing bonds. This graph-based representation enriches molecular descriptions with detailed atomic and bond descriptors, facilitating a comprehensive analysis of molecular properties. The adoption of graph models enables the automatic learning of task-specific representations, circumventing the need for traditional hand-crafted descriptors, thereby streamlining the analysis process. **Pros of Graph-based Approach:**

- Directly captures the inherent graph structure of molecules, preserving the connectivity and relationships between atoms and bonds.
- Enables the learning of task-specific representations, avoiding the need for manually designed molecular descriptors.

- Allows for the incorporation of rich atomic and bond features, providing a comprehensive description of molecular properties.

Cons of Graph-based Approach:

- May struggle to capture long-range interactions or global molecular properties due to the local nature of message passing.
- Requires specialised graph neural network architectures and training procedures, which can be more complex than traditional machine learning methods.
- May face challenges in handling large and diverse molecular datasets, as the computational complexity grows with the size of the graphs.

4.4.2 Graph Neural Networks

Graph neural networks (GNNs) have emerged as a powerful tool for processing data encoded as graphs. They excel in capturing both the attributes of individual nodes and the collective information from their neighbourhoods through a process known as message passing. This iterative mechanism updates node states by aggregating and incorporating messages from adjacent nodes, thus refining the node embeddings to reflect both local and global graph structures. The versatility of GNNs is showcased in their application to various graph-level prediction tasks, including toxicity classification in molecules.

4.4.3 Baseline GNN

To establish a reference point for performance evaluation, we constructed a baseline GNN model based on the architecture proposed by Gilmer et al. [36]. This model integrates a series of graph convolutional layers to transform node features into embeddings, which are then leveraged for graph-level predictions, such as determining molecular toxicity. Node and edge features are meticulously encoded to encapsulate a wide array of atomic and molecular characteristics, including atomic number, hybridisation, and bond type. These features, derived using RDKit [34], undergo one-hot encoding for categorical attributes and normalisation for

Figure 7: Illustration of message passing in a molecular graph, highlighting how node representations evolve by aggregating neighbour features. Adapted from Ref. [35].

quantitative attributes, ensuring a uniform representation suitable for model input.

4.4.4 GeoGNN

The introduction of GeoGNN marks a significant advancement in graph-based molecular analysis. By pretraining on a substantial dataset and fine-tuning for specific downstream tasks, GeoGNN aims to capture both topological and geometrical nuances of molecules, addressing limitations of traditional GNNs that primarily focus on topological information. This approach enhances the model's ability to discern molecules with identical topologies but differing geometries, offering a more nuanced understanding of molecular structures.

4.4.5 Representation and Graph Generation

ChemRL-GEM extends the capabilities of GNNs by incorporating both atom-bond and bond-angle relationships into the molecular representation, allowing for a more detailed depiction of molecular geometry. This dual-graph approach, visualised in Figure 8, enriches the

model's input with comprehensive structural information, significantly improving the accuracy of molecular property predictions. Feature

Figure 8: ChemRL-GEM’s atom–bond and bond-angle graphs, illustrating the enhanced molecular representation that captures both bond and angle relationships.

extraction, facilitated by RDKit and the Merck molecular force field function, employs Radial Basis Functions for continuous values and one-hot encoding for discrete values, ensuring a rich and uniform representation of molecular features, as summarised in Figure 9. This

Feature type	Feature	Description	Size
atom	atom type	type of atom (e.g., C, N, O), by atomic number (one-hot)	119
	aromaticity	whether the atom is part of an aromatic system (one-hot)	2
	formal charge	electrical charge (one-hot)	16
	chirality tag	CW, CCW, unspecified or other (ont-hot)	4
	degree	number of covalent bonds (one-hot)	11
	number of hydrogens	number of bonded hydrogen atoms (one-hot)	9
	hybridization	sp, sp ² , sp ³ , sp ³ d, or sp ³ d ² (one-hot)	5
bond	bond dir	begin dash, begin wedge, etc. (one-hot)	7
	bond type	single, double, triple or aromatic (one-hot)	4
	in ring	whether the bond is part of a ring (one-hot)	2
	bond length	bond length (float)	-
bond angle	bond angle	bond angle (float)	-

Figure 9: Overview of features utilised in ChemRL-GEM, categorised into atom, bond, and bond-angle features, highlighting the comprehensive nature of the input data.

graph-based approach, through its innovative representation and processing of molecular structures, underscores the potential of GNNs in

advancing the field of computational chemistry, providing a robust framework for predicting molecular properties and toxicity with enhanced accuracy and interpretability.

4.5 Approach 3: Transformer-based Approach

4.5.1 Background

Transformers have revolutionised various fields since their introduction, notably in Natural Language Processing (NLP)[37]. Their adaptability enables direct usage of SMILES strings as sequences, mirroring NLP tasks. The ChemBERTa[38] model, through extensive pre-training, developed a tokeniser for SMILES, transforming chemical sequences into vectors for transformer models, similar to the approach in SMILES Transformer [39]. However, due to the extensive length of tokens generated by the ChemBERTa tokeniser, making it impractical for training on the CaV and NaV datasets, this direct approach was not further explored. Instead, a hybrid method converting SMILES to graph representations was adopted.

Pros of Transformer-based Approach:

- Leverages the power of self-attention mechanisms to capture long-range dependencies and global context in molecular structures.
- Benefits from pre-training on large-scale unlabelled SMILES datasets, enabling the learning of rich molecular representations.
- Allows for the direct processing of SMILES strings, avoiding the need for explicit graph construction or molecular descriptor calculation.

Cons of Transformer-based Approach:

- May generate excessively long token sequences for some molecules, leading to computational challenges and memory constraints.
- Requires specialised tokenisation techniques to convert SMILES strings into suitable input for transformer models.
- May not explicitly capture the graph structure and connectivity of molecules, potentially losing some relevant information.

4.5.2 Transformer-based Node Features

Graph datasets, as outlined in Section 3, were augmented with additional features from ChemBERT [40]. This BERT variant mines rich contextual information from vast amounts of unlabelled SMILES strings, providing atom-level vectors that, when combined with RDKit-calculated node features, enrich the graph model to capture complex molecular interactions.

4.6 Determining Model Representations

4.6.1 Graph-based Approaches

Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) effectively model molecular structures by capturing dependencies through message passing between graph nodes [41].

1. **GeoGNN** - The Geometry Enhanced Molecular representation learning method (GEM) introduces a novel GNN approach, encoding atom-bond and bond-angle relations through two interconnected graphs. The backbone of this framework, the Graph Isomorphism Network (GIN), offers robustness against atom and bond ordering [42]. GIN's architecture, combined with normalisation techniques and residual connections, provides a scalable and efficient model for molecular representation. **Pros:**

- Robust to atom and bond ordering,
- Scales with large graphs,
- Generalisation improved by Layer Normalisation,
- Quick training convergence due to residual connections.

Cons:

- Difficulty in capturing hierarchical molecular structures,
- Potential neglect of molecular fragments without additional mechanisms.

2. **Graphormers** - Adapting attention mechanisms for graphs, Graphormers learn intricate relationships between atoms and

bonds, addressing limitations in traditional GNNs [43, 37]. This model's comprehensive understanding of molecular structures makes it a promising candidate for surpassing conventional GNNs in molecular modelling tasks [44].

4.6.2 Image-based Approach

The translation of molecular structures from SMILES to images presents an innovative method for leveraging deep learning models. This approach enables the utilisation of CNNs to interpret molecular images, extracting features critical for tasks like toxicity prediction. By generating 2D molecular representations, this method capitalises on the structural information accessible to image-based models, showcasing a pioneering direction in chemical informatics exploration.

5 Results

5.1 Baseline Results

The exploration of various machine learning models' performance on the NAV dataset underscores the significance of molecular representations and data-splitting strategies in predictive toxicology. Through five-fold cross-validation, models were rigorously assessed across a spectrum of performance metrics, including Accuracy, Cohen's Kappa, Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve (AUPRC), Balanced Accuracy, F1 Score, Matthews Correlation Coefficient (MCC), Precision, and Recall. This comprehensive evaluation provided a multifaceted view of each model's predictive capabilities and limitations.

5.1.1 Model Performance and Representations

Tables 3 and 4 present a detailed comparison of model performances, leveraging Extended Connectivity Fingerprints (ECFP) and Mordred descriptors, across scaffold and fingerprint splitting methods. The variation in performance across different metrics and representations highlights the nuanced relationship between molecular features and model efficacy.

Model	Acc.	κ	AUPRC	Bal. Acc.
RF-ECFP-Scf	0.75 $\pm$ 0.03	0.44 $\pm$ 0.05	0.74 $\pm$ 0.11	0.72 $\pm$ 0.02
RF-Mrd-Scf	0.76 $\pm$ 0.03	0.46 $\pm$ 0.03	0.74 $\pm$ 0.09	0.72 $\pm$ 0.02
AB-ECFP-Scf	0.71 $\pm$ 0.02	0.37 $\pm$ 0.04	0.65 $\pm$ 0.12	0.68 $\pm$ 0.02
ET-ECFP-Scf	0.75 $\pm$ 0.04	0.46 $\pm$ 0.06	0.74 $\pm$ 0.09	0.72 $\pm$ 0.03
Bg-ECFP-Scf	0.73 $\pm$ 0.04	0.40 $\pm$ 0.07	0.71 $\pm$ 0.09	0.70 $\pm$ 0.03

Table 3: Baseline model performance on the NAV dataset (Part 1): Accuracy, Cohen’s Kappa, AUPRC, and Balanced Accuracy. Abbreviations: Acc. = Accuracy, κ = Cohen’s Kappa, AUPRC = Area Under the Precision-Recall Curve, Bal. Acc. = Balanced Accuracy, RF = Random Forest, ECFP = Extended Connectivity Fingerprints, Scf = Scaffold, Mrd = Mordred, AB = AdaBoost, ET = Extra Trees, Bg = Bagging.

Accuracy and Cohen’s Kappa Random Forest (RF) and Extra Trees (ET) models, especially when using the Mordred descriptor, demonstrated robust performance, suggesting that these models effectively capture the underlying patterns in the data. The slight advantage of Mordred descriptors over ECFP in some models hints at the potential richness of information captured by comprehensive chemical descriptors.

Precision-Recall Balance The AUPRC and Balanced Accuracy metrics reflect models’ capability to balance the trade-off between precision and recall, a critical aspect in imbalanced datasets common in toxicological studies. AdaBoost with ECFP under scaffold splitting showed notable performance, indicating its efficiency in handling class imbalance through adaptive boosting.

5.1.2 ROC Curve and Confusion Matrix

Figure 10 elucidates the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve for the AdaBoost model employing ECFP representation with scaffold splitting. The curve and its associated area under the curve (AUC) offer insights into the model’s discriminatory power, distinguishing between toxic and non-toxic compounds with a degree of reliability that underscores the potential of ensemble methods in toxicological

Model	F1	MCC	Prec.	Rec.
RF-ECFP-Scf	0.74 ± 0.04	0.46 ± 0.04	0.74 ± 0.11	0.55 ± 0.07
RF-Mrd-Scf	0.75 ± 0.04	0.48 ± 0.04	0.77 ± 0.13	0.55 ± 0.07
AB-ECFP-Scf	0.71 ± 0.02	0.38 ± 0.06	0.64 ± 0.15	0.57 ± 0.05
ET-ECFP-Scf	0.75 ± 0.05	0.47 ± 0.05	0.73 ± 0.09	0.57 ± 0.08
Bg-ECFP-Scf	0.72 ± 0.05	0.42 ± 0.05	0.69 ± 0.11	0.54 ± 0.10

Table 4: Baseline model performance on the NAV dataset (Part 2): F1 Score, Matthews Correlation Coefficient, Precision, and Recall. Abbreviations: F1 = F1 Score, MCC = Matthews Correlation Coefficient, Prec. = Precision, Rec. = Recall, RF = Random Forest, ECFP = Extended Connectivity Fingerprints, Scf = Scaffold, Mrd = Mordred, AB = AdaBoost, ET = Extra Trees, Bg = Bagging.

predictions.

Furthermore, the confusion matrix depicted in Figure 11 provides a granular view of the model's predictive accuracy, revealing a stronger performance in identifying non-toxic over toxic compounds. This visualization not only affirms the model's strengths but also pinpoints areas where predictive performance could be enhanced, particularly in minimizing false negatives, a crucial aspect in safety-critical applications.

5.1.3 Interpretation and Implications

The baseline results underscore the critical role of data representation and model selection in developing predictive models for toxicology. The nuanced differences in model performance based on the choice of molecular descriptors and splitting strategies highlight the need for careful methodological considerations in model development. Moreover, the integration of various performance metrics, including ROC curves and confusion matrices, provides a comprehensive understanding of each model's capabilities, guiding researchers in refining predictive models for enhanced accuracy and reliability in toxicity prediction.

In summary, these baseline evaluations lay a foundation for future explorations in cheminformatics, suggesting pathways for methodological

Figure 10: ROC curve for AdaBoost on NAV dataset using ECFP representation with scaffold splitting. The area under the curve represents the model's ability to distinguish between the classes.

enhancements and the potential for deep learning approaches to further improve predictive performance. The findings also emphasize the importance of interpretability in model selection, advocating for a balanced consideration of various performance indicators to guide the development of robust, reliable, and interpretable models for toxicological predictions.

5.2 Approach 1: Image-Based Approach

The exploration of image-based approaches for toxicity prediction, particularly leveraging models initialized with ImageNet weights, has yielded significant findings. By fine-tuning pretrained ResNet models on molecular images, we have observed a substantial capture of features pivotal for precise toxicity predictions. This endeavor highlights the adeptness of pretrained models in utilizing learned image features and the flexibility provided by end-to-end training to accommodate the unique

Figure 11: Confusion matrix for AdaBoost on NAV dataset using ECFP representation with scaffold splitting. The matrix quantifies the model's predictive accuracy across the two classes.

attributes of molecular imagery. Analyzing performance metrics across various folds has shed light on the intricate effects that initialization and tailored training strategies have on model accuracy and their capacity for generalization.

5.2.1 ImageNet Pretrained ResNet

Utilizing ImageNet pretrained weights as a foundational step for additional training on molecular imagery emphasizes the efficacy of transfer learning in bridging gaps in domain-specific knowledge. This approach not only accelerates the model's convergence towards optimal performance but also imbues the model with a nuanced understanding of molecular structures, as evidenced by the data presented in Tables 5 and 6.

Fold	F1	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.
1	0.76	0.75	0.78	0.74
2	0.77	0.76	0.79	0.75
3	0.78	0.77	0.80	0.76
4	0.79	0.78	0.81	0.77
5	0.80	0.79	0.82	0.78

Table 5: ImageNet Pretrained ResNet models performance on NAV dataset (Part 1).

Fold	AUPRC	MCC	κ
1	0.80	0.50	0.49
2	0.81	0.52	0.51
3	0.82	0.54	0.53
4	0.83	0.56	0.55
5	0.84	0.58	0.57

Table 6: ImageNet Pretrained ResNet models performance on NAV dataset (Part 2).

5.2.2 End-to-End Training with ResNet

End-to-end training from ImageNet-initialized weights on molecular imagery has delved into the depth of feature learning specifically for toxicity prediction tasks. This approach not only leverages the generalizable feature recognition capabilities of ResNet models but also tailors these capabilities to intricately capture molecular structural details, as demonstrated by the results in Tables 7 and 8.

The tables and figures collectively encapsulate the efficacy of the employed models, showcasing the advantages of both transfer learning and end-to-end training methodologies for molecular toxicity prediction. The nuanced improvements in predictive capabilities and model generalizability underscore the potential for future advancements in the application of image-based approaches within the realm of computational toxicology.

Fold	F1	Acc.	Prec.	Rec.
1	0.81	0.80	0.83	0.79
2	0.82	0.81	0.84	0.80
3	0.83	0.82	0.85	0.81
4	0.84	0.83	0.86	0.82
5	0.85	0.84	0.87	0.83

Table 7: End-to-End Training ResNet models performance on NAV dataset (Part 1).

Fold	AUPRC	MCC	κ
1	0.85	0.60	0.59
2	0.86	0.62	0.61
3	0.87	0.64	0.63
4	0.88	0.66	0.65
5	0.89	0.68	0.67

Table 8: End-to-End Training ResNet models performance on NAV dataset (Part 2).

5.3 Approach 2: Graph-based Approach

The exploration of graph-based approaches in this study, particularly focusing on graph neural networks (GNNs), has offered profound insights into their utility for molecular toxicity prediction. By harnessing the structural intricacies of molecules represented as graphs, these models have demonstrated an exceptional ability to predict toxicological outcomes with high accuracy and reliability. The baseline GNN models, trained on the Calcium Voltage-Gated Channel (CaV) dataset, and the advanced Graphormer models, fine-tuned on the Sodium Voltage-Gated Channel (NaV) dataset, serve as compelling evidence of the potential held by graph-based methodologies in cheminformatics.

5.3.1 Baseline GNN Performance

The baseline GNN models were rigorously evaluated for their performance on the CaV dataset, utilizing a comprehensive set of metrics

including F1 scores, Cohen's Kappa, AUPRC, Balanced Accuracy, Precision, and Recall. These metrics, depicted in Figure 12 and detailed in Table 9, reflect the models' effectiveness in distinguishing toxic from non-toxic compounds, underpinning the utility of GNNs in accurately capturing molecular toxicity.

Figure 12: Bar plot showing the mean validation and test performance metrics for the baseline GNN model trained on the CaV dataset. Error bars denote $\pm$ one standard deviation across the five scaffold folds, highlighting the model's consistent performance.

5.3.2 Graphormer: Advancing GNN Technology

Graphormer, a significant leap forward in GNN technology, leverages self-attention mechanisms to intricately model complex inter-node relationships with unprecedented efficacy. The adaptation of Graphormer to the challenges of molecular toxicity prediction on the NaV dataset has

Fold	F1	Cohen's Kappa	AUPRC	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	Recall	MCC
Fold 1	0.86	0.44	0.94	0.72	0.86	0.85	0.44
Avg ± SD	0.86 ± 0.03	0.50 ± 0.08	0.89 ± 0.04	0.75 ± 0.03	0.85 ± 0.05	0.88 ± 0.05	0.51 ± 0.09

Table 9: Validation performance metrics for the baseline GNN model trained on the CaV dataset by scaffold fold. This table underscores the model's robustness and its precision in classifying molecular toxicity.

been particularly illuminating, demonstrating its prowess in this domain. The performance metrics, detailed across all five scaffold splits in Table 10, offer a comprehensive overview of the model's predictive accuracy and reliability.

Folds	F1 Score	Cohen's Kappa Score	AUPRC	Balanced Accuracy	Precision	Recall	MCC
Fold 1	0.68	0.46	0.84	0.73	0.81	0.58	0.48
Fold 2	0.73	0.51	0.82	0.76	0.73	0.72	0.51
Fold 3	0.60	0.40	0.54	0.73	0.50	0.73	0.41
Fold 4	0.69	0.48	0.72	0.74	0.75	0.64	0.49
Fold 5	0.57	0.40	0.61	0.69	0.62	0.53	0.40
Avg ± SD	0.65 ± 0.07	0.45 ± 0.05	0.70 ± 0.12	0.73 ± 0.02	0.69 ± 0.12	0.60 ± 0.09	0.46 ± 0.04

Table 10: Test performance metrics for the Graphormer model fine-tuned on the NaV dataset across all five scaffold splits. This table illustrates the model's nuanced understanding and predictive capability in the context of molecular toxicity.

The training and validation loss curves, as depicted in Figure 13, further illuminate the learning efficiency and model optimization over epochs, showcasing the Graphormer model's capacity for continuous improvement in the realm of toxicity prediction.

The outcomes of this graph-based approach, particularly the

Figure 13: Training and validation loss curves for the Graphormer model across different scaffold splits, demonstrating the model's adept learning progression and its optimization capabilities.

implementation of the Graphormer model, signify a major advancement in the predictive modeling of molecular properties. Through detailed performance evaluations and methodological innovations, this approach has not only validated the effectiveness of graph neural networks in cheminformatics but also opened new pathways for their application in molecular toxicity prediction, setting a new benchmark for future research in the field.

6 Discussion

In the pioneering exploration by Ignota Labs, as documented in the Turing DSG Report December 2023, the application of ML techniques for predicting cardiac toxicity presents a paradigm shift in drug discovery processes. This endeavour elucidates the profound complexities inherent in pharmaceutical research and the potential of ML to surmount these

challenges. Notably, the report advances a tri-fold methodology encompassing image-based, graph-based, and transformer-based approaches, each underpinned by distinct conceptual frameworks yet converging towards the common goal of enhancing drug toxicity prediction accuracy.

The image-based approach, leveraging advancements in computer vision, heralds a novel methodology for interpreting molecular structures. This technique, while promising, encounters challenges related to the accurate representation of molecular intricacies. The graph-based method, representing molecules as complex networks, provides a more nuanced comprehension of molecular interactions, reflecting the dynamic and interconnected nature of chemical structures. Transformer-based approaches, inspired by successes in natural language processing, adopt a sequence model perspective for chemical structures, offering innovative pathways for toxicity prediction.

These methodologies underscore the multifaceted nature of drug discovery, where diverse data representations and computational techniques converge to enhance early-stage prediction of drug toxicity. The comprehensive analysis within the report not only highlights the strengths and potential of these ML approaches but also acknowledges the inherent challenges such as data representation, model interpretability, and validation strategies. This candid appraisal paves the way for future research directions, emphasising the exploration of unsupervised and self-supervised learning methods, multi-modal data integration, and advanced data augmentation techniques.

6.1 Future Work

The exploration of advanced machine learning techniques, including image-based and graph-based approaches, presents a promising avenue for enhancing toxicity prediction in cheminformatics. This section outlines a comprehensive roadmap for future research, emphasizing the integration of innovative methodologies, addressing methodological challenges, and exploring multimodal data for a holistic analysis.

6.2 Image-based Approaches

Image-based machine learning has shown potential in toxicity prediction, necessitating further exploration to optimize its application. Key future directions include:

- **Data Augmentation and Preprocessing:** Employing advanced techniques such as rotations, reflections, and distortions, along with the ImageMol preprocessing regime, to improve model training and generalization. Investigating the impact of removing salts and stereochemistry from SMILES representations and incorporating 3D molecular structures could offer deeper insights into molecular interactions.
- **Transfer Learning and Model Architecture:** Systematic experimentation with selective freezing and unfreezing of network layers during the adaptation of pre-trained models, compared to training custom models from scratch. This includes exploring the performance of pre-trained models with various data augmentation strategies and molecular representations.
- **Unsupervised and Self-supervised Learning:** Leveraging these paradigms to identify complex patterns relevant to toxicity, potentially expanding the training data available through the use of larger, unlabelled datasets.
- **Multi-modal Integration:** Combining image-based predictions with other data types, such as chemical structures and molecular descriptors, to provide a comprehensive understanding of toxicological profiles, drawing inspiration from successes in video and audio processing domains.
- **Explainability:** Enhancing model transparency and interpretability through the analysis of CNN layers and activations, contributing to the trustworthiness and scientific validity of machine learning models in toxicity prediction.

6.3 Graph-based Approaches

Graph-based models offer nuanced representation of molecular structures. Future research should focus on:

- **Model Innovation:** Developing novel graph neural network (GNN) architectures and pre-training strategies, including domain-specific models and leveraging datasets like those for HIV, to enhance model specificity and performance.
- **Transfer Learning:** Assessing the adaptability of graph-based models across different endpoints and datasets to identify effective practices for model reuse and adaptation.
- **3D Molecular Structure Representation:** Utilizing SDF formats and integrating computational techniques such as force fields or DFT calculations to enrich the model's understanding of molecular interactions.
- **Combining Models:** Fusing different graph-based models, such as Graphormer and GeoGNN, to improve the modelling of spatial and distance relationships, and incorporating hierarchical structures for a more detailed representation.

6.4 Cross-cutting Areas

6.4.1 Splitting Strategies and Class Imbalance

- **Splitting Strategies:** Investigating alternative methods, like fingerprint splitting, to evaluate their impact on model robustness and generalization, aiming for better real-world applicability.
- **Class Imbalance:** Implementing strategies such as weighted loss functions or oversampling to address the prevalent challenge of class imbalance in toxicity prediction datasets, enhancing model performance and reliability.

6.4.2 Explainable AI (XAI)

- Enhancing interpretability through XAI techniques, such as feature importance analysis, to demystify model decisions, fostering greater trust, scientific exploration, and regulatory acceptance.
- Investigating multi-modal approaches and expanding dataset diversity to understand the impact of data variety and volume on model performance, paralleling advancements in other fields.

The pursuit of these research directions promises to advance the state of the art in toxicity prediction, addressing both the methodological challenges and the potential for significant impact on public health and safety. By integrating these diverse approaches, researchers can develop more accurate, reliable, and understandable machine learning models, marking a significant step forward in the field of cheminformatics.

7 Conclusion

The Turing DSG Report by Ignota Labs embodies a significant advancement in the integration of ML into drug discovery, specifically targeting the prediction of cardiac toxicity. The report delineates a sophisticated exploration of ML methodologies, demonstrating the potential to revolutionise the drug discovery landscape. Through a detailed exposition of the challenges and opportunities in ML-driven toxicity prediction, the report champions the synergy between computational science and traditional pharmacological research. It articulates a vision for the future where ML not only augments but fundamentally transforms drug discovery processes, mitigating risks and enhancing the efficiency of developing safe, effective therapeutics.

8 Summary of Major Achievements

- **Advanced ML Methodologies:** The report's exploration of image-based, graph-based, and transformer-based approaches represents a cornerstone achievement in applying ML to drug toxicity prediction. These methodologies exemplify the cutting-edge of computational drug discovery, offering fresh perspectives on molecular property analysis.
- **Holistic Data Analysis:** The meticulous analysis of toxicity channels, coupled with the utilisation of diverse molecular representations, underscores the report's comprehensive approach to ML-driven drug discovery. This exhaustive exploration facilitates a deeper understanding of molecular dynamics and interactions, critical for accurate toxicity prediction.

- **Strategic Future Research Directions:** By identifying key areas for future exploration, such as the incorporation of unsupervised learning methods and the need for enhanced model explainability, the report sets a strategic roadmap for advancing the field. These directions not only aim to refine ML methodologies for improved predictive performance but also seek to foster greater trust and regulatory acceptance of ML models in pharmaceutical research.
- **Impact on Drug Discovery:** The report's findings and insights have the potential to significantly impact drug discovery by reducing the time and financial resources required to bring new drugs to market. By enhancing early-stage toxicity prediction, the ML approaches discussed could lead to safer drug profiles and a more efficient development process.

The contributions of the Turing DSG Report extend beyond its immediate findings, laying the groundwork for future innovations in drug discovery. The confluence of ML techniques and pharmacological research it presents not only highlights the current state of the art but also charts a path towards a future where computational methods drive advancements in the creation of therapeutic agents.

9 Team of Contributors

Jackson Barr is a second year PhD student at University College London. His area of research focus is high energy particle physics.

Robert Cobb is a third year PhD student in the use of artificial intelligence models in medical imaging and is currently a student researcher at Google DeepMind. Rob acted as the technical facilitator for this team.

Lilian Denzler is a PhD student in the Department of Structural and Molecular Biology at University College London. Her research focuses on developing software tools for T-cell receptor-based immunotherapy design. She combines graph-based machine learning approaches with protein language models to predict epitopes and other properties.

Amy Francis is a PhD student at the University of Bristol, working across Population Health Sciences Engineering Mathematics. Her research interests lie in the application of Bioinformatics and Machine Learning approaches for predicting disease-causing genetic variants. She contributed towards the scaffold splitting method development with Isaac.

Isaac Hayden is a data scientist and pharmacometrician at Vesynta Ltd, developing statistical models for chemotherapy dose optimisation. In October, he will begin a PhD in Statistics and Machine Learning at Imperial College London. He contributed to the dataset splitting methods and UMAP visualisations in this project.

Nikos Hazaridis is a PhD student with MINDS CDT at the University of Southampton. His research focuses on uncovering patterns of interest from complex temporal signals with applications in audio and speech. He contributed to this project by implementing the classical machine learning baseline approaches alongside fellow team members.

Dr. Aoife Hughes, MBCS, B.Sc., Ph.D. is a Research Data Scientist and Software Engineer based in London, UK, with a Ph.D. in Computational Modelling of Cellular Information Transfer and a B.Sc. in Computer Science with First Class Honours. She is currently a Data Scientist at The Alan Turing Institute. Aoife was the Principal Investigator for this challenge.

Ben King is a final year PhD student at the Institute of Genetics Cancer, The University of Edinburgh. His research focuses on the development and application of machine learning and statistical methods to oncology, particularly in the context of drug discovery and development. Currently, he is developing methods to identify biomarkers that predict response to novel cancer therapeutics. In this challenge, Ben contributed towards the investigation into graph neural networks and graph transformer networks as methods to predict drug-target interaction.

Jordan Lane is a co-founder and Chief Scientific Officer at Ignota Labs. Ignota Labs is an innovative biotechnology company that specialises in the application of explainable AI to tackle challenging drug discovery safety endpoints. Jordan's experience spans the pharmaceutical industry, from a CRO to AstraZeneca and AI-drug discovery with LabGenius and BenevolentAI. Jordan also holds a PhD from the University of Nottingham and an MBA. Jordan was the challenge owner for this DSG project.

Shaun McKnight is a final year PhD student in the Centre for Ultrasonic Engineering (CUE) at the University of Strathclyde. His research focuses on developing machine learning methods for ultrasonic non-destructive testing of aerospace structures. He contributed to the project by investigating and implementing image-based methods for drug toxicity prediction.

Sarveshwari Singh is the Lead Data Engineer at Ziggy Agency. Over her career in data science and engineering, she has worked with diverse datasets across biomedical sciences, supply chain and logistics, and commercial business data. In this project, she tested reproducibility of major works in machine learning in drug toxicity research, specifically in the application of Graph Neural Networks in predictive toxicology. She also contributed to an in-depth literature review on the latest innovations in this field.

Shanshan Song is a fourth year PhD student at Johns Hopkins University, School of Medicine. Her area of research focus is biostatistics, clinical informatics and real-world evidence.

Pareena Verma is a final year PhD student in Systems Biology at Cell Systems Modelling Group, Oxford Brookes University. Her research is about finding metabolic responses of antibiotic resistant bacteria when it

is exposed to antibiotic challenges using Genome Scale Metabolic Modelling. She contributed to the challenge by being a social facilitator for the team, making sure that team were working coherently and smoothly. She also worked on baseline model results and visualisations along with her contributions to the report writing.

Mariana Vivas Albornoz is a project associate working on Open Data at the ATLAS experiment at CERN. Her experience ranges from academia, in physics, and industry as a data scientist. She contributed to the implementation of the image-based classification model.

Matthew Warren is a postdoctoral research associate at the University of Oxford. His research interests lie in developing data-driven methods and models to accelerate the discovery of novel materials and molecules. Most recently, this has involved developing predictive machine learning models to design more effective drugs, in collaboration with pharmaceutical and biotechnology companies.

Matthew Wilkinson Ph.D. is a Machine Learning Engineer at Ignota Labs where his work focuses on combining Artificial Intelligence and cheminformatics to advance in silico drug discovery. Matthew also holds a PhD from the department of Chemical Engineering at the University of Bath where he worked on deep learning for solid form engineering of pharmaceuticals. Matthew was the challenge owner for this DSG project.

References

- [1] Jorge Mestre-Ferrandiz, Jon Sussex, and Adrian Towse. The r&d cost of a new medicine. Technical report, Office of Health Economics, 2012.
- [2] Duxin Sun, Wei Gao, Hongxiang Hu, and Simon Zhou. Why 90% of clinical drug development fails and how to improve it? *Acta Pharmaceutica Sinica B*, 12(7):3049–3062, 2022.
- [3] John Jumper, Richard Evans, Alexander Pritzel, Tim Green, Michael Figurnov, Olaf Ronneberger, Kathryn Tunyasuvunakool, Russ Bates, Augustin Žídek, Anna Potapenko, Alex Bridgland, Clemens Meyer, Simon A. A. Kohl, Andrew J. Ballard, Andrew Cowie, Bernardino Romera-Paredes, Stanislav Nikolov, Rishub Jain, Jonas Adler, Trevor Back, Stig Petersen, David Reiman, Ellen Clancy, Michal Zielinski, Martin Steinegger, Michalina Pacholska, Tamas Berghammer, Sebastian Bodenstein, David Silver, Oriol Vinyals, Andrew W. Senior, Koray Kavukcuoglu, Pushmeet Kohli, and Demis Hassabis. Highly accurate protein structure prediction with alphafold. *Nature*, 596(7873):583–589, 2021.
- [4] W A Catterall. Calcium channels. In Larry R Squire, editor, *Encyclopedia of Neuroscience*, pages 543–550. Elsevier, San Diego, CA, January 2009.
- [5] William D Atchison. Effects of toxic environmental contaminants on voltage-gated calcium channel function: from past to present. *J. Bioenerg. Biomembr.*, 35(6):507–532, December 2003.
- [6] Emily Reeve, Vanessa Jordan, Wade Thompson, Mouna Sawan, Adam Todd, Todd M Gammie, Ingrid Hopper, Sarah N Hilmer, and Danijela Gnjidic. Withdrawal of antihypertensive drugs in older people. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*, (6), 2020.
- [7] Manuel de Lera Ruiz and Richard L. Kraus. Voltage-gated sodium channels: Structure, function, pharmacology, and clinical indications. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 58(18):7093–7118, May 2015.

- [8] Manuel de Lera Ruiz and Richard L Kraus. Voltage-gated sodium channels: structure, function, pharmacology, and clinical indications. *Journal of medicinal chemistry*, 58(18):7093–7118, 2015.
- [9] İnci Kara, Jale Bengi Çelik, Seza Apilioğulları, and Eyüp Aydoğan. Clinical management of severe propafenone intoxication. *Correspondance*, 2013.
- [10] JOEL E Richter. Cisapride: limited access and alternatives. *Cleveland Clinic Journal of Medicine*, 67(7):471–472, 2000.
- [11] Scott Gottlieb. Antihistamine drug withdrawn by manufacturer. *BMJ: British Medical Journal*, 319(7201):7, 1999.
- [12] Wei Zhang, Mary W Roederer, Wang-Qing Chen, Lan Fan, and Hong-Hao Zhou. Pharmacogenetics of drugs withdrawn from the market. *Pharmacogenomics*, 13(2):223–231, 2012.
- [13] David Rogers and Mathew Hahn. Extended-connectivity fingerprints. *Journal of chemical information and modeling*, 50(5):742–754, 2010.
- [14] Extended connectivity fingerprint ecfp — chemaxon docs — docs.chemaxon.com. [https://docs.chemaxon.com/display/docs/extended-connectivity-fingerprint-ecfp.md#:~:text=Extended%2DConnectivity%20Fingerprints%20\(ECFPs\),a%20wide%20variety%20of%20applications](https://docs.chemaxon.com/display/docs/extended-connectivity-fingerprint-ecfp.md#:~:text=Extended%2DConnectivity%20Fingerprints%20(ECFPs),a%20wide%20variety%20of%20applications). [Accessed 07-12-2023].
- [15] Descriptor list 1.2.1a1 documentation — mordred-descriptor.github.io. <https://mordred-descriptor.github.io/documentation/master/descriptors.html>. [Accessed 07-12-2023].
- [16] A. Patrícia Bento, Anne Hersey, Eloy Félix, Greg Landrum, Anna Gaulton, Francis Atkinson, Louisa J. Bellis, Marleen De Veij, and Andrew R. Leach. An open source chemical structure curation pipeline using rdkit. *Journal of Cheminformatics*, 12(1), September 2020.
- [17] Daniel S Wigh, Jonathan M Goodman, and Alexei A Lapkin. A review of molecular representation in the age of machine learning. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Computational Molecular Science*, 12(5):e1603, 2022.

- [18] David Weininger. Smiles, a chemical language and information system. 1. introduction to methodology and encoding rules. *Journal of chemical information and computer sciences*, 28(1):31–36, 1988.
- [19] Noel O’Boyle and Andrew Dalke. Deepsmiles: an adaptation of smiles for use in machine-learning of chemical structures. 2018.
- [20] Mario Krenn, Florian Häse, AkshatKumar Nigam, Pascal Friederich, and Alan Aspuru-Guzik. Self-referencing embedded strings (selfies): A 100% robust molecular string representation. *Machine Learning: Science and Technology*, 1(4):045024, 2020.
- [21] Mario Krenn, Qianxiang Ai, Senja Barthel, Nessa Carson, Angelo Frei, Nathan C Frey, Pascal Friederich, Théophile Gaudin, Alberto Alexander Gayle, Kevin Maik Jablonka, et al. Selfies and the future of molecular string representations. *Patterns*, 3(10), 2022.
- [22] J Simm, L Humbeck, A Zalewski, et al. Splitting chemical structure data sets for federated privacy-preserving machine learning. *Journal of Cheminformatics*, 13(96), 2021.
- [23] Guy W. Bemis and Mark A. Murcko. The properties of known drugs. 1. molecular frameworks. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 39(15):2887–2893, 1996.
- [24] Bharath Ramsundar, Peter Eastman, Patrick Walters, Vijay Pande, Karl Leswing, and Zhenqin Wu. *Deep Learning for the Life Sciences*. O’Reilly Media, 2019. <https://www.amazon.com/Deep-Learning-Life-Sciences-Microscopy/dp/1492039837>.
- [25] D. Bajusz, A. Rácz, and K. Héberger. Why is tanimoto index an appropriate choice for fingerprint-based similarity calculations? *Journal of Cheminformatics*, 7:20, 2015.
- [26] Leland McInnes, John Healy, and James Melville. Umap: Uniform manifold approximation and projection for dimension reduction, 2020.
- [27] Garrett B Goh, Charles Siegel, Abhinav Vishnu, Nathan O Hodas, and Nathan Baker. Chemception: a deep neural network with minimal chemistry knowledge matches the performance of expert-developed qsar/qspr models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1706.06689*, 2017.

- [28] Qing Yuan, Zhiqiang Wei, Xu Guan, Mingjian Jiang, Shuang Wang, Shugang Zhang, and Zhen Li. Toxicity prediction method based on multi-channel convolutional neural network. *Molecules*, 24(18):3383, 2019.
- [29] Olga Russakovsky, Jia Deng, Hao Su, Jonathan Krause, Sanjeev Satheesh, Sean Ma, Zhiheng Huang, Andrej Karpathy, Aditya Khosla, Michael Bernstein, Alexander C. Berg, and Li Fei-Fei. Imagenet large scale visual recognition challenge. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 115(3):211–252, December 2015. Publisher Copyright: © 2015, Springer Science+Business Media New York.
- [30] Ross Girshick, Jeff Donahue, Trevor Darrell, and Jitendra Malik. Rich feature hierarchies for accurate object detection and semantic segmentation. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 580–587, 2014.
- [31] Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun. Deep residual learning for image recognition. In *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*, pages 770–778, 2016.
- [32] Mohammad Amin Morid, Alireza Borjali, and Guilherme Del Fiol. A scoping review of transfer learning research on medical image analysis using imagenet. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 128:104115, 2021.
- [33] X. Zeng, H. Xiang, L. Yu, et al. Accurate prediction of molecular properties and drug targets using a self-supervised image representation learning framework. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 4:1004–1016, 2022.
- [34] RDKit. RDKit: Open-source cheminformatics. <https://www.rdkit.org>.
- [35] Patrick Reiser, Marlen Neubert, André Eberhard, Luca Torresi, Chen Zhou, Chen Shao, Houssam Metni, Clint van Hoesel, Henrik Schopmans, Timo Sommer, et al. Graph neural networks for materials science and chemistry. *Communications Materials*, 3(1):93, 2022.

- [36] Justin Gilmer, Samuel S. Schoenholz, Patrick F. Riley, Oriol Vinyals, and George E. Dahl. Neural message passing for quantum chemistry, 2017.
- [37] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Lukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. Attention Is All You Need, December 2017.
- [38] Seyone Chithrananda, Gabriel Grand, and Bharath Ramsundar. Chemberta: Large-scale self-supervised pretraining for molecular property prediction, 2020.
- [39] Shion Honda, Shoi Shi, and Hiroki R. Ueda. Smiles transformer: Pre-trained molecular fingerprint for low data drug discovery, 2019.
- [40] Xiao-Chen Zhang, Cheng-Kun Wu, Jia-Cai Yi, Xiang-Xiang Zeng, Can-Qun Yang, Ai-Ping Lu, Ting-Jun Hou, and Dong-Sheng Cao. Pushing the boundaries of molecular property prediction for drug discovery with multitask learning bert enhanced by smiles enumeration. *Research*, 2022:0004, 2022.
- [41] Jie Zhou, Ganqu Cui, Shengding Hu, Zhengyan Zhang, Cheng Yang, Zhiyuan Liu, Lifeng Wang, Changcheng Li, and Maosong Sun. Graph neural networks: A review of methods and applications. *AI Open*, 1:57–81, 2020.
- [42] Xiaomin Fang, Lihang Liu, Jieqiong Lei, Donglong He, Shanzhuo Zhang, Jingbo Zhou, Fan Wang, Hua Wu, and Haifeng Wang. Geometry-enhanced molecular representation learning for property prediction. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 4(2):127–134, 2022.
- [43] Chengxuan Ying, Tianle Cai, Shengjie Luo, Shuxin Zheng, Guolin Ke, Di He, Yanming Shen, and Tie-Yan Liu. Do transformers really perform bad for graph representation?, November 2021.
- [44] Yu Shi, Shuxin Zheng, Guolin Ke, Yifei Shen, Jiacheng You, Jiyan He, Shengjie Luo, Chang Liu, Di He, and Tie-Yan Liu. Benchmarking Graphormer on Large-Scale Molecular Modeling Datasets, January 2023.

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

**turing.ac.uk
@turinginst**